

Event metadata

Event title	Scaling up bioinformatics with ABLeS, the Australian BioCommons Leadership Share
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	12/03/2024
Time of event	12pm AEDT
Topic description	<p>The Australian BioCommons Leadership Share (ABLeS) supports access to, and efficient use of, national computational systems for big-data bioinformatics. Designed for established life sciences projects, groups, institutes and consortia, ABLeS can be used to facilitate software optimisation and scaling, implementation of optimised software for production analyses, and creation of reference data.</p> <p>This webinar highlights how ABLeS is being used by life science communities across Australia to access and leverage bioinformatics at scale. We'll explain the structure of the ABLeS program and how your life science community can get involved, as well as providing a breakdown of the program expectations and the support available from the BioCommons and our partners. Community members making use of ABLeS will share their perspective on the program, and the research outcomes that have resulted.</p> <p><i>ABLeS is supported by the Australian BioCommons in partnership with Bioplatforms Australia, the National Computational Infrastructure, and the Pawsey Supercomputing Centre.</i></p> <p>Speakers: Australian BioCommons: Dr Steven Manos Dr Johan Gustafsson Dr Ziad Al Bkhetan</p> <p>ABLeS users: Dr Hardip Patel, National Centre for Indigenous Genomics, John Curtin School of Medical Research, Australian National University</p>

	<p>Chelsea Mayoh, Zero Childhood Cancer, Children's Cancer Institute</p> <p>Theodore Allnutt, Royal Botanic Gardens Victoria</p>
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/ables
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Computational biology Computational infrastructure
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	This webinar is for life scientists, bioinformaticians and other members of life science communities who are seeking access to computational infrastructure and resources to support their work.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of this webinar you should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List examples of how ABLeS is being used by life science communities across Australia • Outline the structure of the ABLeS program • Identify how your life science community can get involved • Outline program expectations and the support available from the BioCommons and partners
Speakers	<p>Speakers: Australian BioCommons: Dr Steven Manos Dr Johan Gustafsson Dr Ziad Al Bkhetan</p> <p>ABLeS users:</p>

	<p>Dr Hardip Patel, National Centre for Indigenous Genomics, John Curtin School of Medical Research, Australian National University Chelsea Mayoh, Zero Childhood Cancer, Children's Cancer Institute Theodore Allnutt, Royal Botanic Gardens Victoria</p>
Related material	None